

Self-made bucket traps by the Dutch Butterfly Conservation

In 2017 the Dutch Butterfly Conservation invented a new trap with LED to boost the number of locations for the monitoring scheme. To stimulate other monitoring schemes as well we want to make available the specifications of the parts we have used. We use a 15.000 mAh power bank, on which the LED strip burns all night long. Thereby egg boxes are needed which we placed inside the bucket.

A simple bucket. We used a 27-litre bucket. Make a round hole in the lid so the funnel fits. Be aware that they are very light, so on windy places you have to attach them to the ground.

- [We ordered here](#)

Funnel (14 cm height, top opening 21.5 cm and hole in the bottom 6 cm). At the top there is an edge of 1 centimeter.

- Because these are not readily available, we had them made.

Be aware that most of the power banks are 5 volt and the LEDstrip require 12 volt. In that case you need an inverter. We used one which was processed in the USB. Use some of these keywords: “Diymore USB charger USB Adapter DC 5V to DC 12V”

- For example [here](#)

12 volt light switch. An automatic switch which turn on the LEDstrip when it gets dark. Be aware that when you use this, you also need to put in something that asks the whole time a small amount of electricity (we used a small resistor) because otherwise the power bank will switch off after 30 seconds. There are plenty on the internet and try some of these keywords: "Photocell Street Light Switch DC 12V"

3 plexiglas plates. In the middle some free space to hang the pvc tube with the LEDstrip. In our case they are 30cm high and 10.5 cm wide. The wide and the angle at the bottom are depended on the size and type of the funnel.

- Since we could get them regular, we had them made.

With door steps (there is another name for it) on the funnel the Plexiglas plates stay in place.

LEDstrip. We used a 50 cm and non-waterproof one, since the waterproof one influences the rubber outside the LED what makes them less effective. This one works about twice as good as the Philips 6 watt actinic. The strip was rolled around a 21 cm pvc tube to hang them between the three Plexiglas plates.

- [We ordered here](#)

